

FLUCTUATIONS OF TEMPERATURE REGIMES IN THE DIFFERENT SEASONS INDUCES VARIABLE SECRETORY DYNAMICS IN THE CEREBRAL NEUROSECRETORY ELEMENTS IN *LYMNAEA (RADIX) LUTEOLA* WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO SUDAN BLACK B STAIN

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ABSTRACT

The investigation reveals the adoption of method Sudan Black B (SBB) yields a good positive result of the cerebral ganglionic neurosecretory elements of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* exposed to various temperatures. Incidentally a good positive intensity of the stain is being elicited when the animals are kept in the different fluctuating temperature regimes ([low (4°C, 10°C), near ambient (20°C, 25°C) and high (30°C, 35°C)] on their secretory dynamics.

Concomitant with this, the histochemical nature of the neurosecretory material has also been recorded. In all the profiles of study individuals exposed to near ambient temperature are being considered as normal. And finally, the histochemical analyses are made under different temperature regies on the cerebral neurosecretory elements to ascertain correlative biochemical changes.

KEYWORDS: Sudan Black B (SBB), Neurosecretory materials (NSM), Secretory dynamics, Pal Kovit's formula, Hypo-Hyper & Near ambient temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

Protein components of Neurosecretory materials (NSM) probes to be ubiquitous and possibly the term Peptidergic neurons are apparently applied in both vertebrates and invertebrates. Several investigators successfully demonstrated the lipid compound in the NSM in several invertebrates with adoption of Sudan Black B method. Histochemical analysis of the secretory material in the said ganglion is made to assess the biochemical nature of the elaboration.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The materials used in the present investigation are full grown *Lynaea (Radix) luteola* size ranging from 1.2 cm to 1.5 cm. Individual specimens are subjected to different temperature regimes- Near Ambient, hypo and hyperthermal conditions in separate B.O.D. Chambers.

HISTOPHYSIOLOGICAL STUDIES

Investigations were made on the basis of staining intensities, of features morphological stainable granules, their quantity and distribution, size of the cell bodies and nuclei in terms of volume determination by using Palkovit's formula (1963). The activity of the cells in question were assessed as per the formulation devised by Hartwick-nucleoplasamic indices (Np index)-cited by De Robertis (1968). Incidentally, the cells of either large or medium dimensions are taken into account for the diagnosis of their criteria.

GENERAL HISTOCHEMISTRY

Sudan Black B (SBB) method (McManus, 1946) for genral lipid. Fixative- aqueous Bouin's fluid.

OBSERVATIONS

Sudan Black B (SBB)

1. HYPOTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 4°C

Distribution of lipid positive material within the neurosecretory cell groups portrays variability. Cells of larger dimension ordinarily register more SBB-positive substances when compared with the smaller ones (Fig. 1). But, in any case, granular consistency of lipid-positive substances has not been well understood. Axonal processes may contain these substances but in such cases clear cut identity of granular material is seldom visualised. Nuclei are lightly responsive but nucleoli may show more positive reaction (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Section showing the localisation of SBB-positive material within the neurosecretory complements. Note relatively rich reaction of cells of larger dimension and clarity of nucleoli as well as intranuclear material; note also the accumulation of SBB-positive material at the axon hillock region. X 125.

AT 10°C

The extent of reaction is near identical but the clarity of the nuclei is not that pronounced as observed in the preceding hypothermic individuals. SBB-positive reaction of the cytoplasm in the vicinity of the nuclei is more than what is found at peripheral region which may bear lipid positive granules (Fig. 2). These criteria explicit in cells of larger dimension. Small cells ordinarily have moderate reaction and sometimes show lipid-positive material along their axonal courses.

Fig. 2. Section showing distribution of lipid positive granules within the neurosecretory cell bodies. Note nuclei with less conspicuous nucleoli, orientation of the lipid positive granules along the axonal process via axon hillock amongst large cells. X 532.

2. EXPOSURE TO NEAR AMBIENT TEMPERATURE

AT 20°C

Overall response to lipid reaction is waning. Nuclei, too, show deep black very poor reaction. Incidentally, the cytoplasm contain particles which are uniformly distributed throughout the perikarya. Axonal processes may bear lipid positive material but their course within the neuropile is hardly traceable (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3. Section showing the neurosecretory elements having variable intensity of lipid reaction. Note dispatch of SBB-positive material along the axonal processes. X 125.

AT 25°C

Distribution of lipid positive material within the cell bodies reflects a normal pattern and in tune with secretory norms of the cells in question. Nuclei are distinguishable from that of cytoplasm. The latter is, however, endowed with varied concentrations of lipid positive material. sometimes localisation of lipids is convincingly attributed at the axon hillock regions or at posterior portion of the cell concerned. But their availability along the axonal tract is difficult to singularise

Fig. 4. Section showing differential reactive response to SBB reaction to register fluctuating content of lipid positive material. Note clarity of the nuclei as well as axon-hillock areas, X 125.

3. HYPERTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 30°C

Intensity of lipid reaction is elevated as and when comparison is made with the preceding experimental Individuals. Hyperthermic condition seems to trigger disturbance in the cell architecture and necessarily a disarray in the distribution of lipid positive material ensues. Nuclei are distinguishable from the cytoplasm since the former have a very weak reaction. These criteria are noticeable in cells of large dimensions (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Section illustrating a single large cell containing SBB-positive materials within the perikaryon along the axonal process. Note ill-defined architecture of both the nucleus and cell body. X 532.

AT 35°C

The extent of reaction has a striking feature and in commensurate with the cytoarchitectural aberrations. Indeed, majority of the cells feature identifiable despite of having intense stainability do not granules. In general, the nuclei possess less stainability and assume Irregular contour. Seldom granular consistency of the lipid positive material (Fig. 6) may be detected along the axonal processes.

Fig. 6: Section demonstrating deep stainability for the cells following adoption of SBB method. Note symptoms of structural aberrations to cell bodies and lack of granular conformity amongst SBB positive substances. X 125.

Table 1: Showing alterations in the histochemical profiles of cerebral neurosecretory cells of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* under the variable temperature regimes.

Methods adopted	Reacting sites/groups	Hypothermal		Near Ambient		Hyperthermal	
		4° C	10° C	20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C
Sudan Black B (SBB)	S-S group	+/-	+/+	+/+	+/-	+++	+/-

+/- Doubtful reaction

+/+/+/+ Reactions of increasing intensity

Series 1,2: Reactions of increasing intensity.

Series 3: Doubtful reaction intensity of Sudan Black B (SBB) reaction is well documented in the Hypothermal and Near Ambient temperatures but in the hyperthermal situation the same intensity dwindles.

DISCUSSION

Localisation of bound lipids in the neurosecretory perikarya, irrespective of the several phyla of invertebrates has been cited in clear terms (Faser, 1959; Ganguly, 1962; Nanda and Goswami, 1978; Sadana and Kaur, 1980; Majumder, 1983; Rajlakshmi Bhanu et al., 1983; Bandyopadhyay, 1987 and Tarafdar, 1988). Negative or very weak intensities of reaction of bound lipid for NSM in some species may be interpreted due to "strong binding" so as to render the lipoprotein in laminated form (Sjöstrand, 1953) to have a least affinity for the fat soluble colouring agents by steric hindrances (Berenbaum, 1958) or depends on the acidophilic nature of NSM endowed with protein rich in tyrosine (Boer, 1965). Affinity for bound lipid with neurosecretory elaboration of some molluscs like *L. stagnalis* (Böer, 1965), *Mytilus viridis* (Nagabhushanam, 1974) and *Lamellidens* 1965), *Mytilus marginalis* (Tarafdar, 1988) is obvious. Necessity for the masked lipid has been highlighted to designate it as "labile barrier" for guarding the neurohormone from various interactions that may develop from different cell constituents (Berenbaum, 1958; Ganguly, 1962; Nanda and Goswami, 1978; Tarafdar, 1988). In the present investigation, the distribution of bound lipid in the cerebral neurosecretory cells of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* is in consonance with the observations of Nagabhushanam, 1974 and Tarafdar, 1988. Fluctuation in the distribution of acetone Sudan black B positive material amongst the brain neurosecretory perikarya exposed

to three major temperature regimes has been considered to be linked with the secretory efficacy since role of lipoprotein in the functioning of subcellular organelles like endoplasmic reticulum is noteworthy. In any event, bound lipid moiety of the neurosecretory substances seems to be imperative in the secretory kinetics of the cells concerned (Bhaumik, 1984; Tarafdar, 1988). Near ambient temperature treatment engenders moderate to weak response in contrast with the low temperature exposure which most of the time reflects a good positive reaction. But subjection to high doubtful reaction. temperature incites very circumstances, it may be presumed that role of masked lipid is in a state of disarray following ectothermic stress.

CONCLUSIVE REMARK

Effects of both high and low thermal exposures encompass some salient changes with respect to the abundance substances, electron dense granules and their disposition within the of heterochromatin microtubular processes, appearances of the cytoplasmic fibrillar elements etc. Such changes from one temperature regime to other provide clues to ascertain the structure-function relationship in the context of the secretory behaviour of the cells concerned. This is specially pertinent when environmental flux in the natural habitat of the species under study is considered (Nanda *et. al.*, 2023, 2024 & 2025).

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